

A CLINICAL CASE REPORT ON AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF RAKTAJA ABHISHYANDA W.S.R TO VIRAL CONJUNCTIVITIS

Dr. Shreenidhi*¹, Dr. Rathi S.²

¹Final Year PG Scholar, Department of Shalaky Tantra, GAMC, Bengaluru-09.

²Professor, Department of Shalaky Tantra, GAMC, Bengaluru-09.

Government Ayurveda Medical College, Dhanvantari Road, Bengaluru, Karnataka-560009.

Article Received on 15 March 2026,
Article Revised on 04 April 2026,
Article Published on 16 April 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19593123>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Shreenidhi

Final Year PG Scholar, Department
of Shalaky Tantra, GAMC,
Bengaluru-09.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Shreenidhi*¹, Dr. Rathi S.² (2026). A Clinical Case Report On Ayurvedic Management Of Raktaja Abhishyanda W.S.R To Viral Conjunctivitis. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(8), 679-685.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Abhishyanda is one of the *Sarvakshigata Rogas* described by *Acharya Sushruta*. Among them *Raktaja Abhishyanda* is characterized by features such as *Tamrasrava* (coppery red discharge), *Lohita Netrata* (redness of eyes), *Raji* (engorged blood vessels) and *Daha* (burning sensation) in the *Netra*. In modern terms, conjunctivitis refers to inflammation of the conjunctiva, presenting with redness, discharge, watering, irritation, and photophobia. Viral conjunctivitis, most commonly caused by adenoviruses, is highly contagious and accounts for 60–80% of infectious cases. In this case report, a 57-year-old male patient presented to our OPD with features resembling viral conjunctivitis, and the diagnosis was made based on clinical examination. Treatment was administered according to Ayurvedic principles, including *Seka*, *Bidalaka*,

for one week. The patient recovered completely within one week, with no recurrence of symptoms during the subsequent 15-day follow-up period. While contemporary management primarily focuses on symptomatic relief through cold compresses and topical medications, the Ayurvedic approach offers effective and holistic management by Correcting *dosha dusti*, thereby promoting safe, cost-effective, and natural healing.

KEYWORDS: *Raktaja Abhishyanda*, *Allergic Conjunctivitis*, *Seka*, *Bidalaka*.

INTRODUCTION

Abhishyanda is one among the seventeen *Sarvakshigata Rogas* mentioned by *Acharya Sushruta* in *Uttaratantra*.^[1] It is also described as an *Aupasargika Vyadhi*. *Acharya Sushruta* has explained four types of *Abhishyanda*, among which *Raktaja Abhishyanda* is one. It is characterized by features such as *Tamrasrutha* (coppery red-colored discharge), *Lohita Netrata* (redness of the eye), *Raji Samantata* (prominent striations of blood vessels), *Daha* (burning sensation), *Paka* (inflammation), *Shishira Abhinanda* (desire for cold), *Dhoomayana* (a sensation as if smoke is coming out), *Ushnasru* (hot lacrimation), and *Bashpa Samucchraya* (excessive lacrimation).^[2] As per Ayurvedic principles, treatments such as *seka*, *bidalaka* and *shamanoushadis* are administered to correct *dosha dusti*.

Conjunctivitis is an inflammation of the conjunctiva, causing redness, watering, discharge, and irritation of the eye. It may be infectious (viral or bacterial) or non-infectious (allergic or chemical). Viral conjunctivitis is a highly contagious condition, most commonly caused by adenoviruses. It accounts for 60–80% of infectious conjunctivitis cases, especially during community outbreaks, and can affect all age groups.^[3] Often associated with Upper Respiratory tract infection. Common clinical features include sudden redness, watery discharge, ocular discomfort, foreign body sensation, and photophobia.^[4] The conservative line of management includes cold compresses, use of sunglasses to reduce glare, decongestants, lubricant eye drops, and topical antibiotics or antiviral medications.

CASE REPORT

A 57 year old male patient consulted Shalaky Tantra OPD of Government Ayurveda Medical College, Bengaluru with complaints of burning sensation, redness, watery discharge, itching and associated with feeling of hotness in both eyes since 5 days.

History of present complaints

A 57 year old male presented with complaints of burning sensation, redness, watery discharge, itching and associated with feeling of hotness in eyes since 5 days. The symptoms were sudden in onset, Initially noted symptoms in left eye followed by Rt eye. Hence, for the same complaint he visited our hospital for Ayurvedic treatment.

History of past illness

- No previous history of similar severe eye infections in past.

- No history of trauma, ocular surgery, or contact lens usage/chronic eye diseases like glaucoma or uveitis/recent upper respiratory tract infection.
- No history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension or thyroid dysfunction medications.
- No known drug allergies.

Personal and demographic data

- Age: 57 years
- Sex: Male
- Occupation: Agriculture
- Diet: Mixed
- Appetite: Moderate
- Bowel: Constipated
- Micturition: Normal (5-6times day/0-1night)
- Sleep: Normal
- Addiction: Nil
- *Prakriti: Pitta-Vata.*

Table no 1: EXAMINATION :(Before treatment).

	RIGHT EYE	LEFT EYE
Head posture	Normal	Normal
Eye ball	Normal in size and position	Normal in size and position
Eye lid	Normal	Normal
Eye lashes	Normal	Normal
Nasolacrimal duct	Patent	Patent
Conjunctival	Hyperaemia present (bulbar and palpebral conjunctiva)	
Sclera	Normal	Normal
Cornea	Normal	Normal
Anterior chamber	Normal depth	Normal depth
Iris	Normal in colour and pattern	Normal in colour and pattern
Pupil	RRR, 3mm	RRR, 3mm
Lens	SIMC present	SIMC present
UAVA		
Distant vision	6/12 p	6/18p
Near vision	N12	N12

IOP: Right eye -11mm Hg, Left eye -12mm Hg

Table no 2: INTERVENTION.

Date	Drug	Dose	Route of administration	Duration
4/02/2026	1.Sadyo virechana with Trivrit lehya with ksheera	40gm	Oral	1 day
5/02/2026 to 11/02/2026	1.Kashaya Seka ⁵ with Triphala,daruharidra,yastimadhu,lodra (Morning)	QS	LA	7 days
	2.Bidalaka with Mukkadi choorna (Afternoon)	QS	LA	
	FOLLOW UP MEDICINES			
12/02/2026-26/02/2026	1.Bruhat Manjistadi kwatha	10ml BD	Oral	15days
	2.Haridra khanda	1/2tsp BD	Oral	
	3.Triphala Kashaya Eye wash	Qs	LA	15 days
Total duration of treatment				23 days

Table no 3: RESULT AND OBSERVATION.

Treatment sitting	Signs	Symptoms
After Sadyovirechana	Conjunctival congestion reduced by 30%	Watering of eyes reduced by 20% Burning sensation reduced by 30% Itching reduced by 30% Feeling of hotness of eye reduced by 10%
8 th day(After Bidalaka and Seka)	Conjunctival congestion reduced by 95%	Watering of eyes reduced by 95% Burning sensation absent Itching reduced by 90% Feeling of hotness in eyes absent
Follow up (23 rd day)	Conjunctival congestion Absent	All symptoms w.r.t viral conjunctivitis-absent

Figure 1: Before treatment

Figure 2: After (Sadyovirechana)

Figure 3: After (Bidalaka and Seka)

DISCUSSION

MODE OF ACTION

Acharya Sushruta mentioned *Virechana*, *Bidalaka*, *Seka* are the line of treatment in *Raktaja Abhishyanda*.

1. *Kosta Shodhana (Sadyo Virechana)*

In *Ayurveda Koshtha Shodhana* is the primary line of treatment. *Acharya Sushruta* described *Shodhana Karma* in *Raktaja Abhishyanda*. *Trivrut* is a *Sadyovirechaka dravya* does *Shodhana* and *Pitta Rakta Shamana*. *Rechana* of *pitta dosha* will lead to *Rakta Shodhana* due to its *Ashraya Ashrayi Bhava*. Patient got 20-30% relief in the symptoms like itching, burning and watering from the eyes.

2. *Bidalaka*

In this study *Bidalaka* done with *Mukkadi choorna* for a period of 7 days.

Bidalaka refers to the external application of medicated paste over the eyes. It is specifically indicated in managing acute inflammatory ocular symptoms such as *Ruja* (pain), *Daha* (burning sensation), and *Raga* (redness). *Mukkadi Yoga*, a formulation described in the classical text *Sahasrayogam*^[6] is one such preparation mentioned under *Urdhwagata Roga Chikitsa*.

Mukkadi choorna contains drugs like *Triphala*, *Gairika*, *Rakta Chandana*, *Haridra*, *Daruharidra*, *Lodra*, *Sariva*, *Durva*, *Usheera*, *Nimba*. These drugs contains *Deepana*, *pachana*, *Chakshushya*, *Raktapittashamana*, *Kandughna* and *Dahaprashamana* properties.

When applied over the eyelids, the drug gets absorbed through the skin and exerts both local and systemic effects, aiding in vasodilation and facilitating the removal of accumulated toxins from the affected area. The ingredients of *Mukkadi Yoga* are predominantly cooling in nature, making it effective in pacifying vitiated *Pitta* and *Rakta*. It does transdermal action with a *Pittashamaka* effect. Additionally, its mildly acidic nature may enhance the function of *Brajaka Pitta*, thereby supporting better absorption and therapeutic efficacy through the skin.

3. *Kashaya Seka*

In this study *Seka* done with *Triphala*, *Daruharidra*, *Yastimadhu*, *Lodra* for 7 days.

Table no 4: Dravya karmukata.

<i>Dravya</i>	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Guna</i>	<i>Virya</i>	<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Karma</i>
<i>Triphala</i>	<i>Kashaya pradhana lavana varjitha pancha rasa</i>	<i>Laghu,ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosahara Chakshusya</i>
<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Kashaya,tiktha rasa</i>	<i>Laghu,ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>katu</i>	<i>Pittahara</i>
<i>Yastimadhu</i>	<i>Madhura rasa</i>	<i>Guru,Snigdha</i>	<i>Sheeta virya</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridosahara Chakshusya</i>
<i>Lodra</i>	<i>Kashaya, katu</i>	<i>Laghu,ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Pitta hara</i>

Seka refers to the continuous instillation or pouring of a medicated liquid into a closed eyes for a specified duration. It provides prolonged contact of the drug with ocular tissues, improving its therapeutic action. It is particularly indicated during the acute stage of inflammation, The absorption of the medicated solution through the conjunctival epithelium and corneal epithelium helps in alleviating the signs and symptoms of *Raktaja Abhishyanda*.

Seka, when administered warm, acts as *Sthanika Swedana*, promoting vasodilation, improving local metabolism, and reducing hyperemia and burning sensation. Additionally, the local application helps in cleansing the ocular surface by removing inflammatory debris, discharge, allergens, and microbes, thereby relieving irritation and infection. The herbal medicaments used in *Seka* further contribute through their anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.

4. Brihat manjistadi Kashaya: Internally administrated in *Nirama Avastha*. It does *Raktha shodhana* and *Shamana of Pitta, Raktha dosha*.

5. Haridra khanda: Contains drugs like *Haridra, Daruharidra, Trivrut, Shunti, Maricha*. Taken internally does Anti inflammatory and Immunomodulatory action.

6. Triphala Kashaya Eyewash: Helps in removing *Srava(Discharge)* and *Netra kandu(Itching)* due to its Anti septic, Anti inflammatory and Antioxidant action.

CONCLUSION

Mukkadi Choorna Bidalaka along with *Kashaya Seka* was found to be effective in reducing the signs and symptoms of *Abhishyanda*, with notable improvement observed following treatment. No adverse or toxic effects were reported during or after the course of therapy. In contemporary practice, management often includes systemic anti-inflammatory drugs,

analgesics, and ocular ointments, which may sometimes lead to unwanted side effects such as ocular irritation. In contrast, Ayurveda emphasizes *Netra Kriyakalpas* like *Bidalaka* and *Seka*, along with appropriate *Shamana Aushadhis*, not only for symptomatic relief but also for preventing recurrence. Hence, the use of *Mukkadi Bidalaka* and *Kashaya Seka* can be considered a safe and effective approach in the management of *Abhishyanda*. The outcome observed in this case was encouraging and merits documentation.

REFERENCE

1. Acharya NRK, ed., Sushruta Samhitha with the Nibandhasangraha Commentary of Sri Dalhanacharya and the Nyayachandrika Panjika of Sri Gayadasacharya on Nidanastana, Uttaratantra 6th chapter, 3-4th verse, Varanasi: Chaukamba Krishnadas academy, 2014; 603.
2. Acharya NRK, ed., Sushruta Samhitha with the Nibandhasangraha Commentary of Sri Dalhanacharya and the Nyayachandrika Panjika of Sri Gayadasacharya on Nidanastana, Uttaratantra 6th chapter, 9th verse, Varanasi: Chaukamba Krishnadas academy, 2014; 604.
3. Kanski JJ, Bowling B. Clinical Ophthalmology: A Systematic Approach. 9th ed. Elsevier, 2020; 124–128.
4. Khurana AK, Khurana B. Comprehensive Ophthalmology. 7th ed. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers, 2019; 78–80.
5. Acharya NRK, ed., Sushruta Samhitha with the Nibandhasangraha Commentary of Sri Dalhanacharya and the Nyayachandrika Panjika of Sri Gayadasacharya on Nidanastana, Uttaratantra 12th chapter, 9th verse, Varanasi: Chaukamba Krishnadas academy, 2014; 616.
6. K.V. Krishnan Vaidyan & S. Gopala Pillai, Sa-hasrayogam, 33rd edition, Vidyarambham Pub-lishers, Mullakkal, Alappuzha, Feb 2015; page no. 381.